

POSTBUCKLING AND FAILURE OF STIFFENED COMPOSITE PLATES

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SUMMARY: Postbuckling and failure were studied analytically and experimentally for the stiffened composite plates. In the analysis, the stiffened composite plates were analyzed using the nonlinear finite element method. The progressive failure analysis was done by adopting the maximum stress criterion and complete unloading failure model. In the failure analysis, the considered failure modes are matrix failure, shear failure and fiber failure. In the experiment, the stiffeners were formed by the continuous lay-up of the skin. Therefore, the separation between the stiffener and the skin was not found even after final failure. A shadow moire technique was used to monitor the out-of-plane deformations of the plates. Piezoelectric film sensors were attached to the plate and damages were detected by those. The analytical results on the buckling load, postbuckling behavior, and failure characteristics showed good agreement with the experimental results. The stiffened composite plate, which had been fabricated by secondary bonding, was failed by debonding between the skin and the stiffener. The comparisons of the present cocuring with the secondary bonding for the stiffened composite plate were conducted with respect to postbuckling behavior and failure mode in experiments.

KEYWORDS: postbuckling, failure, stiffened composite plate, cocuring, debonding

INTRODUCTION

The stiffened composite plates are extensively used in aircraft and other structural components to satisfy requirements of increased stiffness and reduced weight. Since the buckling of the stiffened plates does not mean the total collapse of structure, it has been found to be efficient to permit buckling of the stiffened composite plates under postbuckling ultimate load. Therefore, it is essential to investigate the postbuckling behavior and failure characteristics of the stiffened composite plates. In most of previous studies [1, 2, 3] except for ref. [4], the stiffened composite plates have been secondarily bonded between the skin and the stiffener or cocured without ply overlap in the junction part of the skin and the stiffener. These types of the stiffened composite plates losed load carrying capacity due to the separation between the skin and the stiffener. In case of the previous study [3], the postbuckling compressive strength of the secondary bonded plate was higher than that of the cocured one about 18%. In present study, the separation of the cocured plate was eliminated by curing the stiffener with the skin in a continuous laminate. In the analysis, a progressive failure model was introduced into the nonlinear finite element analysis[5, 6]. This finite element program was applied to the stiffened composite plate fabricated by the present cocuring. The postbuckling behavior and the failure characteristics were studied. Two kinds of the stiffened composite plate, which had been fabricated by present cocuring and secondary

bonding respectively, were also tested to compare postbuckling behavior and failure modes in experiments.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The eight-node degenerated shell element is used for the modeling of the stiffened composite plates, and the first order shear deformation theory is adopted in the nonlinear finite element analysis. To estimate the failure load of each failure mode, the maximum stress criterion is applied to the average stresses in the principal material directions of each layer of each element. Also, in order to estimate the postbuckling load-carrying capacity, it is assumed that the stress corresponding to the failure mode of each layer is completely unloaded and the corresponding stiffness is set to zero in each element. This complete unloading failure model can be expressed by the following equations.

If fiber failure occurs, then

$$\sigma_1 = 0, \quad E_1 = 0, \quad \nu_{12} = 0, \quad \nu_{13} = 0$$

If matrix failure occurs, then

$$\sigma_2 = 0, \quad E_2 = 0, \quad \nu_{21} = 0, \quad \nu_{23} = 0$$

If shear failure occurs, then

$$\tau_{12} = 0, \quad \tau_{21} = 0, \quad G_{12} = 0$$

The failure of each element in this model is estimated for the converged stresses during each load step, and the stress component corresponding to the failure mode is unloaded. Therefore, if failure occurred at the previous load step, the force equilibrium is not satisfied at the first iteration of the present load step, and an unbalanced force is induced due to the unloaded stress component. For the postbuckling failure analysis, the effect of the deformation due to the failure-induced unbalanced force should be introduced into the modified arc-length method[5, 6]. In case of modeling the skin and the stiffener with the degenerated shell elements, the incompatibility in degrees of freedom arises from the difference in local coordinates between the two elements to hold the adjacent nodes of the skin and the stiffener in common. The compatibility is enforced to the common nodes by equalizing the displacement in the global x , y , z directions and matching the rotation about the local unit vector.

EXPERIMENTS

The stiffened composite plates were fabricated using graphite/epoxy prepreg, and the material properties used in this study were as follows.

$$E_1=130.0 \text{ GPa}, E_2=E_3=10.0 \text{ GPa}, G_{12}=G_{13}=4.85 \text{ GPa}, G_{23}=3.62 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.31, \\ \nu_{23}=0.52, X_T=1933 \text{ MPa}, X_C=1051 \text{ MPa}, Y_T=51 \text{ MPa}, Y_C=141 \text{ MPa}, S=61 \text{ MPa}$$

The geometry and the dimension of the stiffened plate are shown in Fig. 1-a. Boundaries are clamped for loaded edges and free along the unloaded sides. The stiffened plate consists of

two stiffeners having the lay-up sequence of $[0/90/45/0/-45]_5$ for web and cap. The stiffeners were formed by the continuous lay-up of skin, $[0/90/\pm 45]_5$. As shown in Fig. 1-b, two types of the stiffeners were used in the composite plates, one was I-shaped stiffeners, and the other was blade-shaped stiffeners. Two 0° plies for the flange were inserted into the skin, and one of them was continued to the stiffener. Unidirectional tape fillers were inserted into intersection between the web and the skin or the cap. After curing, the stiffened plates were inspected using C-scan and no significant defects were detected. The loaded ends of the stiffened plates were potted by casting resins, and they were machined flat and parallel to load uniformly. The stiffened plates were tested to final failure in compression to investigate its postbuckling behavior. Out-of-plane deflections were also monitored by the shadow moire technique. Piezoelectric film sensors were used to detect the event of damages globally.

Fig. 1-a: Geometry of I-stiffened plate.

Fig. 1-b: Configuration of stiffeners.

To compare postbuckling behavior of the present cocuring with the secondary bonding, two stiffened composite plates were also fabricated by different method. In case of the secondary bonding, the skin and the stiffener were precured firstly. The typical surfaces of the skin and the stiffener, which would be bonded each other, were abraded with a mesh sandpaper such as #150. The surface roughness was $3\mu\text{m}$ in the direction of fiber and $9\mu\text{m}$ in the vertical direction. American Cyanamid FM-73 adhesive films were inserted into the surface between the skin and the stiffener and cured in an autoclave.

COMPARISON OF ANALYSIS WITH EXPERIMENT

The load-end shortening curves of the I-shaped stiffened plate obtained from experiment and finite element analysis are shown in Fig. 2. The stiffened composite plate carried the applied load about four or five times of the buckling load. The experimental buckling load is in good agreement with the analytical result. But the experimental postbuckling ultimate load differs by 23% from the analytical result because the failure model used in this paper does not consider the delamination. The positions of the first-ply-failure of each mode are indicated on the load-end shortening curve. These failure modes induced the reduction in the stiffness of the plate abruptly. At last the load carrying capacity was lost rapidly. The separation between the stiffener and the skin was not found even after the final failure. The buckling loads were determined by the load- deflection curves at the center of the plate, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2: Load-shortening curves of I-stiffened plate.

Fig. 3: Load-deflection curves of I-stiffened plate.

Fig. 4: Contour plots of out-of-deflection

Figure 4 shows the contour plot of the out-of-plane skin deflections generated from the finite element analysis and the photograph of the moiré fringe pattern at the point A. These results show very good agreement in postbuckling range. Figure 5-a shows the picture of the stiffened plate after final failure. Delaminations were occurred along the free edges and fiber failures were occurred at the stiffener. Figure 5-b shows the failure pattern of that in analysis. Most of failures were occurred at the center of the stiffeners and the free edges.

Fig. 5-a: Failure patterns in experiment.

Fig. 5-b: Failure patterns in analysis.

The load-end shortening curves of the blade-shaped stiffened plate obtained from experiment and finite element analysis are shown in Fig. 6. The experimental postbuckling ultimate load differs by 2% from the analytical result. The first-ply failure of analysis was occurred at the point A and damage in experiment was detected near the final failure. Figure 7 shows the event of damage detected by piezoelectric film sensors.

Fig. 6: Load-shortening curves of blade-stiffened plate.

Fig. 7: Piezoelectric film signal due to internal damage.

COMPARISON OF COCURING WITH SECONDARY BONDING

Figure 8 shows two I-shaped stiffeners formed by the present cocuring and the secondary bonding respectively. For both specimens, unidirectional tape fillers were inserted into the intersection between the stiffener and the skin. Figure 9 shows the load-shortening curves of stiffened composite plates loaded in the axial direction. The slopes of load-shortening curves

Fig. 8: Two types of the stiffened plate.

Fig. 9: Load-shortening curves of cocured plate and bonded plate.

matched till the point A but decreased after the point A in cocured case, because the stiffener of the bonded plate sustained more compression load than that of the cocured plate until the peeling was occurred between the skin and the stiffeners. The postbuckling compressive strength of the cocured plate was slightly smaller than that of the bonded plate. But present cocured stiffened plate showed relatively higher postbuckling compressive strength than previous ones[2, 3], when compared with secondary bonded plate.

Fig. 10: Load-strain curves of cocured plate.

Fig. 11: Failure patterns of cocured plate.

Figure 10 shows load-strain curves of the cocured plate in the skin and the stiffener. In case of skin, the slope of load-strain curve changed at the event of buckling due to the bowing of the skin. But otherwise the slope of load-strain curve of the stiffener changed little till the point A. Therefore the stiffener sustained the compressive load in the axial direction and the skin sustained bending moment till the point A. The slope of the load-strain curve increased in the skin and decreased in the stiffener after the point A, because the buckling mode of the skin was enlarged globally and the bending moment had effects on the stiffener. Figure 11 shows the patterns of failure before final collapse. The stiffener had delaminations under the stiffener due to bending moment. The separation between the stiffener and the skin was not found. Figure 12 shows load-strain curves of the bonded plate in the skin and the stiffener. The slope of the load-strain curve in the stiffener changed little till the point A, because the stiffener with adhesive film sustained compression load till the debonding. The debonding between the skin and the stiffener was occurred suddenly after the point A, as shown Fig. 13.

Fig. 12: Load-strain curves of bonded plate.

Fig. 13: Failure patterns of bonded plate.

CONCLUSIONS

The finite element program with the progressive failure model was applied to the stiffened composite plates under axial compression. The postbuckling behavior and the failure of these plates were characterized. The stiffeners were fabricated by the continuous plies of the skin and cocured with the skin. Therefore, the separation between the stiffener and the skin, which was main failure mode of the previous cocured or bonded plates, was not found even after final failure. The events of damage were detected by piezoelectric film sensors in experiments and compared with analysis. The results of FEM about the buckling load, the postbuckling behavior, and the failure characteristics showed good agreement with those of experiments. The postbuckling compressive strength of the cocured plate was slightly smaller than that of the bonded plate. But the present cocured stiffened plate showed relatively higher postbuckling compressive strength than previous ones, when compared with the secondary bonded plate. The bonded stiffened plate lost the loading carrying capacity suddenly due to the debonding between the skin and the stiffener, which was not found in the present cocured plate.

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